

Potentiometric studies on the complexes of sulfamethazine and sulfathiazole with some metal ions

Mahmoud A. Ghandour^a, Ensaf Aboul-Kasim^{b*}, A. H. Amrallah^b, Nadia A. Abdalla^b and O. A. Farghly^b

^aChemistry Department, Faculty of Science, Assiut, Egypt

^bChemistry Department, Faculty of Science, Aswan, Egypt

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The interaction of Th^{IV}, UO₂^{II}, Cu^{II}, Cd^{II}, Zn^{II}, Ni^{II}, Pb^{II}, Fe^{III} and Al^{III} ions with sulfamethazine (SMZ) and sulfathiazole (STZ) has been followed potentiometrically. The stability constants of the formed chelates are determined at 25° and $\mu = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaNO₃) in 50% (v/v) aqueous ethanol medium. The complexes have 1 : 1 and/or 1 : 2 metal-ligand ratio depending on the nature of the ligand or metal ion. The protonation constants of the two ligands are also determined.

Sulfanilamide and its *N*¹-substituted compounds are well-known sulfa drugs¹. Monosubstitution at *N*¹ has furnished the bacteriostatically most active derivatives². Metal complexes of sulfa drugs play a vital role in metabolic and toxicological function in biological systems³. Many sulfa drugs show increased biological activity when administered in the form of metal complexes⁴. The interaction of metal ions with some sulfa drugs has been studied using potentiometric method at different temperatures and ionic strengths⁵⁻⁷.

The present communication aims to study the possibility of the complex formation of the metal ions Th^{IV}, UO₂^{II}, Cu^{II}, Cd^{II}, Zn^{II}, Ni^{II}, Pb^{II}, Fe^{III} and Al^{III} with ligands sulfamethazine (SMZ) and sulfathiazole (STZ).

Results and Discussion

Representative titration curves are shown in Fig. 1. The values of \bar{n}_A determined by the method of Irving and Rossotti⁸ were calculated from the titration data using solutions (a) and (b) for both ligands SMZ and STZ. Proton-ligand association constants were calculated from \bar{n}_A against pH plot. The values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ (the first and second proton association constants of both the ligands SMZ and STZ) are the pH values corresponding to $\bar{n}_A = 0.5$ and 1.5 respectively. It is observed that these data (Table 1) disagree with those reported earlier⁷. This may be attributed to using ethanol medium (50%, v/v) and that the empirical correction to pH meter reading in ethanol medium was not accounted.

The titration curves of the metal-ligands solution are well separated from the ligand solutions for both SMZ and STZ. Thus, replacement of hydrogen ions is due to complexation. From these titration curves, \bar{n} (average number of ligands molecules attached per metal ion) and pL (free ligand expo-

Fig. 1. Distribution diagram for (—) UO₂^{II} - SMZ and (---) Fe^{III} - SMZ systems.

*Present address : Faculty of Education, Chemistry Department, El-Kharga Oasis, New Valley, Assiut University, Egypt.

ment) values were calculated⁸. The \bar{n} values were plotted against the corresponding pL values to get the formation curves of the metal complexation equilibria. From these formation curves, the stability constants were determined using the half-integral and mid-point calculation methods⁸ (Table 1). Also the least-squares method⁹ was used to get the refined value of formation constants. The value of σ_{fit}

Table 1. Dissociation constants of the ligands STZ and SMZ and stability constants of metal ions complexes

Temp. = $25 \pm 1.0^\circ$, $\mu = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaNO_3), medium : 50% (v/v) ethanol.

Ion	Ligand STZ		Ligand SMZ	
	log K_1	log K_2	log K_1	log K_2
H ⁺	2.51 (2.36)	8.35 (7.12)	2.25 (2.36)	8.5 (7.37)
Fe ^{III}	8.57	7.98	-	8.30
Al ^{III}	8.55	6.45	-	6.70
Th ^{IV}	8.30	7.72	8.26	7.90
UO ₂ ^{II}	7.15	5.55	6.40	5.84
Cu ^{II}	5.15 (4.52)	- (3.47)	5.44 (3.81)	- (3.73)
Pb ^{II}	4.05	-	4.26	-
Zn ^{II}	3.95	-	3.65	-
Cd ^{II}	3.85	-	5.08	-
Ni ^{II}	3.43	-	3.35	-

Value in parenthesis are taken from Ref. 7.

(standard deviation) is 0.022. The stoichiometry of the chelates depends on the nature of the metal ion and ligand. Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} ions form 1 : 1 metal-ligand chelates with both the ligands (SMZ and STZ), while Th^{IV}, UO₂^{II}, Al^{III} and Fe^{III} ions form 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 metal-ligand chelates with STZ. In the case of SMZ, Th^{IV} and UO₂^{II}, form 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 chelates, whereas Fe^{III} and Al^{III} form only 1 : 2 metal-ligand chelates. SMZ and STZ have two sites bearing protons. The first site is *N*-pyridine (SMZ) or *N*-thiazole (STZ) ring and the second one is sulfonamido (-SO₂NH-) group. The protons may be dissociated from these sites in proportions which vary with the degree of neutralization. It is suggested that the structures of SMZ and STZ chelates are similar to Cu^{II} chelates of some sulfa-drugs and also the structures are supported by the ir studies of metal-sulfa-drugs complexes⁶.

The stability constants of these complexes follow the order : Th^{IV} > UO₂^{II} > Cu^{II} > Pb^{II}, Zn^{II} > Cd^{II} > Ni^{II} in the case of STZ, and Th^{IV} > UO₂^{II} > Cu^{II} > Pb^{II} > Cd^{II} > Zn^{II} > Ni^{II} in the case of SMZ. This is in accordance with Irving-Williams¹⁰ order and the expected decrease in the ionization

potential of the metal ions in the same direction and electronegativity¹¹. Malecki *et al.*⁷ determined the pK_a's of the SMZ and log K values for Cu^{II} complex (Table 1). These values are in disagreement with our results. This may be attributed to the use of different media.

From the species distribution diagrams, the percentage of the mole fraction of different species (metal ion and complexes) were calculated¹² using the obtained stability constants and the initial concentrations of the metal ions and ligands in the pH range 1.0–7.0. The species distribution curves can be obtained by plotting the percentage of the mole fraction of the species versus pH. Representative curves are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. Closely related plots were obtained for other systems. The plots reveal that at low pH value, the metal ions are often present as free ions. This indicates no complex formation in the acidic medium. On increasing the concentration of the ligand by increasing the pH of the solution during the titration, the percentage of the free metal ion tends to decrease, while that of ML species tends to develop at moderately acidic media. However, the

Fig. 2. Distribution diagram for (—) UO₂^{II} - STZ and (---) Fe^{III} - STZ systems.

value of $\log K_1 K_2 (\beta_2) > \log K_1 (\beta_1)$ indicates that there will be an appreciable concentration of ML_2 species in this pH region; with the further increase in the pH of the solution, the essential change is the increase in the concentration of ML_2 with decrease in ML . Above this region almost all of the metal ions remain in the form of ML or ML_2 species and their concentration increases on increasing the pH of the solution. Also some percentages of species at intersection points and maximum pH and $\log(L)$ for SMZ and STZ complexes were calculated and it is found that the values of $\log(L)$ at the intersection points (αM , αML) and (αML , αML_2) are very close with the values of stability constants for each of metal-ligand complex under study.

Experimental

Calvin-Bjerrum technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti⁸ was used to determine the protonation constants of the ligands and formation constants of the metal complexes at 25° in 50% (v/v) aqueous ethanol medium.

pH was measured on an Orion 601A pH meter. During the titration, oxygen-free nitrogen was bubbled through the solution. The electrode system was calibrated in terms of hydrogen-ion concentration instead of activities. The solutions of metal ions (A.R., B.D.H.) were standardized¹³. Sulfamethazine (SMZ) and sulfathiazole (STZ) (Sigma) solutions were prepared fresh in absolute ethanol. A series of solutions, each of initial volumes 50 ml, in 50% (v/v) aqueous ethanol, ionic strength 0.1 mol dm⁻³ (NaNO₃) were prepared having the following compositions: (a) 0.01 mol dm⁻³ HNO₃ + 0.09 mol dm⁻³ NaNO₃, (b) solution a + 0.01 mol dm⁻³ of SMZ or STZ, (c) solution b + 0.002 mol dm⁻³ solution metal ion, and titrated with a standard 0.1 mol

dm⁻³ NaOH solution in the same solvent medium and having the desired ionic strength at 25 ± 1.0°.

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